

Formation of Heterocyclic Compounds. Part I. Action of Methyl-dithiocarbazinate upon *ortho*- Diketones and their Monoximes, and upon Chlorides and Esters of Dibasic Acids.

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The object of undertaking the present investigation was to make a comparative study of the behaviour of the *o*-diketones and their monoximes with other compounds possessing the grouping $\text{-NH}\cdot\text{NH-}$ e.g., hydrazines, semi- and thiosemi-carbazides, thiocarbohydrazide, on the one hand and with methyl-dithiocarbazinate on the other. Curtius (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1881, **44**, 168, 188; *Ber.*, 1889, **22**, 2161) obtained different types of compounds by the action of hydrazine upon several *o*-diketones. Thiele and Stange (*Annalen*, 1894; **283**, 1) studied the action of thiosemicarbazide upon benzil and obtained a triazine compound. Schmidt and his collaborators (*Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 276, 3250) obtained a semicarbazone of phenanthraquinone and a triazine compound from its oxime. Guha and De (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **2**, 228) obtained closed-ring thiocarbohydrazones from molecular proportions of thiocarbohydrazide and diketones like benzil, acenaphthaquinone, camphorquinone, and alloxan, whereas from two molecules of phenanthraquinone (as also β -naphthoquinone and isatin) and one molecule of thiocarbohydrazide they obtained di-phenanthraquinone-thiocarbohydrazone. Guha and De (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **3**, 41) prepared heptatriazine compounds from molecular proportions of *o*-aminophenylhydrazine and a number of *o*-diketones.

One molecule of methyl-dithiocarbazinate reacts with one ketonic group of phenanthraquinone and acenaphthaquinone to form the corresponding hydrazone methyl dithiocarboxylates as intermediate products, thus:

which then assumes the azo structure by migration of one hydrogen atom,

Similar cases of migration resulting in the change of hydrazones into azo compounds are well known (cf. Liebermann, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2863; Zincke and Lawson, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 2903; Meldola, *Phil. Mag.*, 1888, 11, 411; Guha and De, *loc. cit.*). The azo-compounds then lose a molecule of methyl mercaptan giving rise to oxydiazine compounds (I, II) thus:

With isatin the reaction proceeds thus:—

That this compound contains a thiol group is proved by the fact that it is soluble in alkali and readily gives insoluble lead and mercury mercaptides and monoacetyl and monobenzoyl derivatives.

Benzil reacts with methyl dithiocarbazine with the liberation of hydrogen sulphide and methyl mercaptan. The resulting product possesses a sharp melting point but curious as it appears, it does not contain any nitrogen.

Two molecules of water are eliminated from one molecule of phenanthraquinone monoxime and one molecule of $\text{NH}_2\text{—NH—CSSMe}$ with the formation of a compound possessing the empirical formula $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$, which may be represented by either of the following two formulae.

The osotriazole-methyldithiocarboxylate (IV) on hydrolysis by alkali and on subsequent acidification should yield the free thio-acid and methyl mercaptan. But in actual practice, no such thing was observed. Hence, thioheptatriazine formula (V) is given preference to the osotriazole formula (IV).

Isatin monoxime does not react with the carbazinate showing that the monoxime does not possess any active ketonic group.

The action of six different acid chlorides (*viz.* thionyl, oxalyl, phthalyl, fumaryl, succinyl, carbonyl) upon the carbazinate has been studied. With thionyl chloride the reaction proceeds thus :

This intermediate product then loses another molecule of hydrochloric acid to yield methylthiocarbazine sulphite.*

With oxalyl, phthalyl, fumaryl, succinyl and carbonyl chlorides the reactions proceed in a similar fashion forming respectively 6-keto-5-hydroxy-2-methylthiol-1:3:4-thiodiazine (VII), 2-methylthiol-5-hydroxy-6:7-benzo-1-keto-1:3:1-octathiodiazine (VIII), 2-methylthiol-5-hydroxy-8-keto-1:3:4-octathiodiazine (IX), 2-methylthiol-5-hydroxy-6:7-dihydro-8-keto-1:3:4-octathiodiazine (X) and 2-hydroxy-5-methylthiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XI) thus :

* Cf. similar reactions of 1-substituted thiosemicarbazides with phosgene (Freund, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 4178) and with thiophosgene (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 2843).

A corresponding 8-*N*-phenylthiodiazole compound of type (XI) was prepared by Busch from PhNH.NH.CSSMe by the action of phosgene (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1899, 60, 34). The easy formation of a closed ring compound (IX) from fumaryl chloride in which the COCl groups occupy *trans*-positions with respect to each other can only be explained by assuming a transformation of the *trans* into the *cis* form under the conditions of the experiment.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenanthraquinone and Methyl dithiocarbazinate: Formation of 2-Thion-5:6-phenanthro-1:3:4-oxydiazine (I).

An alcoholic solution of phenanthraquinone (2.1 g.) and methyl-dithiocarbazinate (1.2 g.) was heated under reflux. The reaction began at once as was indicated by the evolution of mercaptanic smell. The solution turned red and a red crystalline precipitate began to separate out. This was filtered hot and recrystallised from pyridine as light red needles, m. p. 205°-206° (yield 2 g.). It is insoluble in dilute alkalis and dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid producing a dark green colouration. (Found: N, 10.10; S, 11.60. C₁₃H₈ON₂S requires N, 10.61; S, 12.12 per cent.).

The above experiment when repeated using 2 molecules of methyl-dithiocarbazinate with one molecule of phenanthraquinone yielded the same compound.

2-Thion-5:6-acenaphtho-1:3:4-oxydiazine (II).

A mixture of acenaphthaquinone (1.8 g.) and methyl-dithiocarbazinate (1.2 g.) was heated in acetic acid solution under reflux for four to five hours. A brownish red solid mass began to separate with the evolution of mercaptanic smell. The separated solid was filtered from the mother-liquor while hot, washed with acetic acid and purified by crystallization from dilute pyridine when needle-shaped crystals were obtained, m. p. 208°-209° with decomposition. It is insoluble in alkali and produces a dark-brown colouration with strong sulphuric acid. Yield 2 gms. (Found: N, 12.07. C₁₃H₈ON₂S requires N, 11.76 per cent.).

2-Thiol-5:6-isato-1:3:4-oxydiazine (III).

By heating isatin (1.5 g.) and methyl-dithiocarbazinate (1.8 g.) in acetic acid solution under reflux, a deep yellow precipitate was

obtained which was crystallized from acetone, m. p. 227° with decomposition. It is soluble in dilute sodium hydroxide solution from which it can be precipitated by hydrochloric acid and gives a red colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 20·30. $C_8H_8ON_2S$ requires N, 20·69 per cent.).

The *benzoyl derivative* prepared by the Schotten Bauman process was crystallised from a very small quantity of acetone, m. p. 238°-229°. Mixed melting point with the original isatin condensation product is 208-209°. (Found: N, 13·11. $C_{10}H_8O_2N_2S$ requires N, 13·68 per cent.).

The *acetyl derivative* was obtained by heating the isatin condensation product with acetic anhydride for about twenty minutes under reflux and then pouring into water. It was purified by repeated crystallisation from water, m. p. 161°-162°. (Found: N, 16·75. $C_{11}H_8O_2N_2S$ requires N, 17·14 per cent.).

Benzil and Methyl-dithiocarbasinate.

A mixture of benzil (2 g.) and methyl dithiocarbasinate (1·2 g.) was heated under reflux in acetic acid solution for 12 hours, during the first four hours' heating there being no appreciable change. The excess of acetic acid was removed by distillation under reduced pressure, the solution was cooled and the small quantity of the yellow substance thus obtained was crystallised from acetone, m. p. 195°. It was found to contain only sulphur, carbon and hydrogen. It is insoluble in dilute caustic soda solution. (Found: S, 44·67 per cent). As the yield of the product was only 0·15 grams, a thorough study of its properties as also an analysis for carbon and hydrogen could not be made.

Phenanthraquinone monoxime and Methyl-dithiocarbasinate: Formation of 3:4-Phenanthra-7-thiomethyl-1:2:5:6-heptathiotriazine (V).

A mixture of phenanthraquinone monoxime (1 g.) and methyl-dithiocarbasinate (1 g.) was heated in alcoholic solution under reflux for about 8 hours. On cooling a brownish red precipitate came out which was crystallised from pyridine in needles, m. p. 209°-210° with decomposition. It is insoluble in dilute cold sodium hydroxide solution. (Found: N, 13·45. $C_{10}H_{11}N_3S_2$ requires N, 13·55 per cent.).

Methyl dithiocarbazine and Isatin Monoxime.

By treating molecular proportions of isatin monoxime and methyl dithiocarbazine in a similar manner as in the foregoing experiment and also by heating the mixture at 100° in a sealed tube for about twelve hours, isatin monoxime was found to have been left unconverted.

Methyl dithiocarbazine Sulphite.

Thionyl chloride (2 g.) in benzene solution was gradually added to a benzene solution of methyl dithiocarbazine (2 g.) when a violent reaction ensued with the separation of a yellowish white solid substance. It was filtered, washed with benzene and crystallised from dilute acetone. The yield was almost quantitative. It shrinks at 100° and melts at 122°-128°. It is soluble in cold sodium hydroxide solution. (Found: N, 17.15. $C_4H_4ON_2S_2$ requires N, 16.67 per cent.).

2-Methylthiol-5-hydroxy-6-keto-1:3:4-thiodiazine (VII).

The solid product obtained by mixing benzene solutions of oxalyl chloride and methyl dithiocarbazine was found to be insoluble in all ordinary organic solvents. It was, however, purified by dissolving in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and fractionally precipitating with dilute hydrochloric acid. The process of fractional precipitation was repeated once again. It melts at 127° with decomposition. (Found: N, 16.83; S, 35.94. $C_4H_4O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 15.91; S, 36.36 per cent.).

The acetyl derivative, prepared in the usual manner, was purified by crystallising twice from dilute alcohol, m. p. 174°-175°. (Found: N, 12.84. $C_6H_6O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 12.84 per cent.).

2-Methylthiol-5-hydroxy-6:7-benzo-8-keto-1:3:4-octathiodiazine (VIII).

The solid product obtained by heating a benzene solution of phthalyl chloride (2 g.) and methyl dithiocarbazine (1.2 g.) under reflux for 5-10 minutes, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining plates. The compound shrinks at 155° and melts at 161°-162°, and is soluble in cold sodium hydroxide solution. (Found: N, 10.76. $C_{10}H_8O_2S_2N_2$ requires N, 11.11 per cent.).

2-Methylthiol-5-hydroxy-8-keto-1:3:4-octathiodiazine (IX).

By proceeding as in the previous experiment, a solid product (2 g.) was obtained from fumaric chloride (1.5 g.) and methyl dithiocarbazine (1.2 g.). The substance could not be crystallised from the common organic solvents; however a saturated solution of the substance in boiling aqueous acetone solution gave, on cooling, a white amorphous precipitate melting with decomposition at 171°. (Found: N, 13.64; S, 31.24. $C_6H_4O_2N_2S_8$ requires N, 13.86; S, 31.68 per cent.).

2-Methylthiol-5-hydroxy-6:7-dihydro-8-keto-1:3:4-octathiodiazine (X).

The solid product (1.5 g.) obtained from succinyl chloride (1.5 g.) and methyl dithiocarbazine (1.2 g.) could not be crystallised from any organic solvent. An aqueous solution of this substance was boiled with animal charcoal for half an hour, filtered, the filtrate evaporated almost to dryness which on cooling gave a yellow crystalline substance, m. p. 137° with decomposition. It turns brownish-red on exposure to the air. (Found: N, 13.96; S, 30.94. $C_6H_4O_2N_2S_8$ requires N, 13.73; S, 31.37 per cent.).

2-Hydroxy-5-methylthiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XI).

A mixture of 4 gms. of 30 % solution of phosgene in toluene and 1.2 gms. of methyl dithiocarbazine suspended in 5 c.c. of toluene was shaken for half an hour in a shaking machine and allowed to stand overnight. Next day, the solid product was washed repeatedly with toluene and was crystallised in needles from a small quantity of water, m.p. 96-97° after shrinking at 91° (yield quantitative). The compound is soluble in cold dilute sodium hydroxide solution. (Found: N, 19.39. $C_5H_4ON_2S_4$ requires N, 18.92 per cent.).

Action of Methyl dithiocarbazine on Oxalic Ester: Formation of (VII).

Oxalic ester (1.5 g.) and methyl dithiocarbazine (1.2 g.) in alcoholic solution were heated at 100° for 12-13 hours in a sealed tube. The solution, on evaporation on a water-bath, yielded a semi-solid mass which when pressed on a porous plate gave a yellowish white solid substance. It was identical with the condensation

product of oxalyl chloride and methyl dithiocarbazinate and was similarly purified. (Found: N, 16.32. $C_4H_4O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 15.91 per cent.).

Condensation of carbonic ester with methyl dithiocarbazinate in alcoholic solution was tried by the method similar to that described in the previous operation, but no reaction was found to have taken place.

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